

Republic of Iraq

Ministry of higher education of research –
High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis & Assisted Reproductive
Technologies

3 – November –2021

To: **Essa Bahauldeen Fadhil**
Mustansiriyah University
Clinical Pharmacy Department

Research approval letter

Dear Mohammad,

**Subject: Impact of Co enzyme Q10 as adjuvant therapy to letrozole on
spermiogram and sex hormone in Iraqi infertile men; A comparative study**

After close review on the proposal. I am glad to inform you that the ethical committee at the “High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis & Assisted Reproductive Technologies” acknowledges the importance of the study and give its formal approval.

Code: A21024

Best regards,
Dean of Institute

